

Supplementary File 1

StatModPredict: A User-Friendly R-Shiny Interface for Fitting and Forecasting with Statistical Models.

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1. Auto-regressive integrated moving average (ARIMA)

Autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models are a commonly employed approach to time series forecasting [1-12], primarily focusing on describing the autocorrelations with the data [13]. ARIMA models consist of three parts: (1) auto-regressive models, (2) moving average models, and (3) integration, which aids in increasing data stability. Additional details regarding the ARIMA model and its associated components can be found in [13].

1.1. Non-seasonal ARIMA models (ARIMA)

Auto-regressive models of order p ($AR(p)$) involve using a linear-type regression of the most recent values of the time series against themselves. The models can capture various time series patterns, thus are robust to different processes of interest. The $AR(p)$ model is given by [13]:

$$y_t = c + \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 y_{t-2} + \phi_p y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where ε_t is white noise, and c is a constant. The parameters ϕ_p capture the data patterns, and y_t are the lagged values of the time series with length t .

Moving average models of order q ($MA(q)$) are identical to (Eq.1). However, they include past forecast errors within the model rather than the auto-correlated data [13]:

$$y_t = c + \varepsilon_t + \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} + \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}. \quad (2)$$

Similar to Eq. 1, ε_t is a white noise process with mean 0 and variance σ^2 , c is a constant, θ_q controls the time series pattern, and ε_{t-q} are the lagged error terms.

When working with a stationary stochastic process whose joint probability distribution does not change with time, both the $AR(p)$ and $MA(q)$ models can be consolidated into an ARMA model [13]:

$$y_t - \phi_1 y_{t-1} - \phi_2 y_{t-2} - \dots - \phi_p y_{t-p} = c + \varepsilon_t + \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}. \quad (3)$$

where the notation follows that described for (Eq. 1) and (Eq. 2). However, when the data shows evidence of non-stationarity and the mean changes over time (i.e., trend), ARIMA (p,q,d) models can be employed as they first involve a differencing (d) step which removes any non-stationary trends. The difference between consecutive observations is computed to differentiate the data, such as $y_t - y_{t-1}$. Then, the ARMA model can be applied to the data after differencing. The ARIMA model is given by [13]:

$$(1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_p B^p)(1 - B)^d y_t = c + (1 + \theta_1 B + \dots + \theta_q B^q) \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

where $(1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_p B^p)y_t$ corresponds to the $AR(p)$ component, B represents the backshift operator, $(1 - B)^d y_t$ corresponds to differencing the timeseries data d times, and the $MA(q)$ component is given by $c + (1 + \theta_1 B + \dots + \theta_q B^q)\varepsilon_t$. Finally, as in (Eq. 1)-(Eq. 3), ε_t is the white noise process in the model.

1.2. Seasonal ARIMA models (SARIMA)

The ARIMA model can also capture various seasonal data patterns, with only a slight adjustment to (Eq. 4) and the process discussed above. To form a seasonal ARIMA model, we include additional parameters, $(P, D, Q)m$ where m represents the seasonal period [13]. Therefore, (Eq. 4) now becomes [13]:

$$(1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_p B^p)(1 - \Phi_1 B^m - \dots - \Phi_P B^{Pm})(1 - B)^d (1 - B^m)^d y_t = c + (1 + \theta_1 B + \dots + \theta_q B^q)(1 + \Theta_1 B^m + \dots + \Theta_Q B^{Qm}) \varepsilon_t. \quad (5)$$

The $AR(p)$, $MA(q)$, and differencing terms are interpreted identical to (Eq. 4). The m parameter indicates the seasonal period, $1 - \Phi_1 B^m - \dots - \Phi_P B^{Pm}$ corresponds to the seasonal $AR(P)$ model, $(1 - B^m)^d y_t$ corresponds to the seasonal differencing and the seasonal $MA(Q)$ model is given by $1 + \Theta_1 B^m + \dots + \Theta_Q B^{Qm}$ [13]. ε_t is the white noise process in the model [13].

1.3. Software Specifications

We employ the *auto.arima()* function from the "forecast" package to automatically select the order values of the ARIMA model based on the specified data and parameter ranges. Additional details regarding the function can be found in [14]. To provide flexibility in model specifications, users can choose values for each of the parameters for the non-seasonal (p, q, d) and seasonal (P, Q, D, m) ARIMA models. We employ the *forecast()* function from the "forecast" package to produce all forecasts and assume the default settings as discussed in [15].

2. Generalized Linear Regression (GLM)

Generalized Linear Models (GLMs) extend linear regression models to allow for multiple types of assumed distributions (i.e., Poisson, Negative Binomial, Gaussian/Normal). The model contains three components: (1) random or stochastic component, (2) systematic component, and (3) link function [16]. As applied in this toolbox, a GLM is structured as follows [16]:

$$g(y_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 t. \quad (6)$$

The random component identifies the response variable, y_t , and its associated probability distribution [16]. As applied in the toolbox, y_t corresponds to the time series data values and can be continuous or discrete counts. Together, the single predictor, t , and the intercept β_0 compose the systematic component of the GLM [16]. Within the toolbox, we assume a simple GLM model with only one predictor t , the time components of the original data (i.e., dates). Finally, the link component ($g(\cdot)$) is responsible for the robust nature of the GLM framework to other error structure types [16]. Specifically, the link function designates a function connecting $E(y_t)$, where $E(y_t) = \mu_t$, and the linear predictor, t [16].

2.1. Distributions

As applied in this toolbox, we utilize three possible distributions: Normal, Poisson, and Negative Binomial.

2.1.1. Normal

The link function for the normal distribution is the identity function. Therefore, when the user selects the normal distribution for the GLM, the given model is the equivalent of simple linear regression (SLR) [16].

2.1.2. Poisson

Poisson regression is a form of GLM that assumes a Poisson distribution, which is used to model counts and has the property of $\sigma^2 = \mu$. Further details regarding the distribution can be found in [17]. As applied in the toolbox, a GLM assuming a Poisson-distributed outcome applies a logarithm link; thus, it is often referred to as a "log-linear". Using (Eq. 6), the application of the Poisson link is as follows [18]:

$$\ln(\mu_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 t. \quad (7)$$

The general function, $g(\cdot)$ introduced in (Eq. 6) is now given as $\ln(\cdot)$ to show the specific function used within Poisson regression.

2.1.3. Negative Binomial

Similar to Poisson regression, negative binomial regression requires count data. However, unlike Poisson regression, Negative Binomial models are more robust to overdispersed data as they allow the variance to exceed the mean [19]. For example, the quadratic mean-variance relationship is given by $\sigma^2 = \mu + \mu^2 / \theta$ [19]. Additional details regarding the estimation of θ can be found in [19]. The link function is identical to that of the Poisson distribution.

2.2. Software Specifications

We employ the $glm()$ function from the "forecast" package to conduct simple linear and Poisson regression [20]. We use the $glm.nb()$ function provided by the "MASS" package when assuming a negative binomial distribution [21]. We utilized the $predict()$ function from the "stats" package to obtain model forecasts and fits [22]. Users can select the underlying distribution assumption (i.e., *Normal*, *Poisson*, or *Negative Binomial*) during model customization. If either *Poisson* or *Negative Binomial* is selected, we exponentiate the resulting model fits and forecasts to return results in the original scale of the data. We use the default settings for each function provided in their respective documentation.

3. Generalized Additive Models (GAM)

Generalized Additive Models (GAM) extend GLMs to include non-linear data patterns while maintaining similar levels of explainability and simplicity [23]. Unlike (Eq. 6), GAM models include a sum of unknown smooth functions of some covariates [24]. Specific to our dashboard, with time as the only covariate, the general structure of the GAM, assuming normality, is as follows [23]:

$$y_t = \beta_0 + z(t) + \epsilon_t \tag{8}$$

where $z(\cdot)$ is an unknown smooth function of time. However, ϵ_t is included only in the model assuming normality and follows $\epsilon_t \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ [17]. The Poisson and Negative Binomial distributions follow that discussed above (for GLM), and both distributions employ a log-link resulting in:

$$\ln(y_t) = \beta_0 + z(t). \tag{9}$$

Regardless of the distribution the user selects, the smooth function $z(\cdot)$ is represented using basis functions (i.e., building blocks for complex functions). The default setting employed within the dashboard uses basis splines or piecewise polynomial functions [25]. Specifically,

$$z(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k b_k(t), \quad (10)$$

where $\{b_k(\cdot)\}$ represent the basis functions, $\{\beta_k\}$ are the expansion coefficients to be estimated, and K is the number of basis functions [23]. Here, the number of basis functions depends on the length of calibration data available for a given forecasting period. Users can also select the specific smoothing term from the following documentation [26]. We set the default to a discrete penalty based on coefficients and then fit the model by solving a penalized least square problem (i.e., ps in [26]). Additionally, users can customize the number of basis functions considered. For any GAM employed within the toolbox, the generalized cross-validation (GCV) criterion selects the smoothness tuning parameter [25].

3.1. Software Specifications

We employ the `gam()` function from the "mcgv" package for model fitting [25]. Users can select the underlying distribution assumption (i.e., *Normal*, *Poisson*, or *Negative Binomial*) during model customization. If either *Poisson* or *Negative Binomial* is selected, we exponentiate the resulting model fits and forecasts to return results in the original scale of the data. Additionally, while the number of basis functions is auto populated based on the length of the calibration period, users can specify the number they wish to employ in the calculation of the smoothing function (Eq. 10). Finally, users can also specify a different smoothing term than the default ps option, selecting one of the options provided in [26]. Once the model has been fit, we utilize the `predict()` function from the "stats" package to obtain model forecasts and fits [22]. Except for the available specifications discussed here, we use the default settings for both functions (`gam()` and `predict()`) provided in their respective documentation.

4. Meta (Facebook's) Prophet Model (Prophet)

Meta (Facebook's) Prophet model has been increasingly employed across multiple fields to forecast different processes of interest [1, 4, 8, 9, 12, 27-31]. The model's specification is similar to that of the GAM

and is decomposable into three primary components: (1) trend, (2) seasonality, and (3) holidays and an error term [32]. Thus, the model has the following form with time as the only regressor [32]:

$$y(t) = g(t) + s(t) + h(t) + \epsilon_t . \quad (11)$$

Here, $g(t)$ represents the non-periodic component for modeling the time series trend. Periodic trends (e.g., seasonal changes) are captured by $s(t)$, and $h(t)$ is an irregular events component used for modeling irregular changes (e.g., holidays or similar events). The component ϵ_t represents the normally distributed model errors at time t . The model is estimated via a Bayesian approach [13]. Additional details regarding the model can be found in [32, 33].

4.1. Non-periodic Component, $g(t)$

Within the dashboard, users can select from *linear* or *uniform* growth trends. When a user chooses the *linear* growth option, $g(t)$ becomes a set of piecewise linear equations where the growth rate varies between change points [32]. Thus, the non-periodic component is given by [32]:

$$g(t) = (k + \mathbf{a}(t)^\top \boldsymbol{\delta})t + (m + \mathbf{a}(t)^\top \boldsymbol{\gamma}) \quad (12)$$

where k is the growth rate, and m is an offset parameter. The Prophet model allows the growth rate to change at various time points or changepoints. Therefore, there are S automatically selected changepoints at time s_j , where $j = 1, \dots, S$ [32]. $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ represents the vector of rate adjustments, where δ_j is the rate change at s_j [32]. The rate at time t is represented by $k + \mathbf{a}(t)^\top \boldsymbol{\delta}$, where [32]:

$$a_j(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } t \geq s_j \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

m , the offset parameter is also adjusted with each change to k . Finally, to ensure a continuous function the adjustment at changepoint j is given by $-s_j \delta_j$. As applied in the dashboard, the changepoints are

automatically selected by setting a sparse prior on δ [32]. Additional details regarding the change points can be found in [32]. If the user selects the "flat" growth option, $g(t)$ becomes a constant value [32].

4.2. Periodic Component, $s(t)$

The seasonal component of the Prophet model, $s(t)$, relies heavily on a Fourier series. Specifically, the model approximates seasonal effects with the following standard Fourier series [32]:

$$s(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N (a_n \cos(\frac{2\pi nt}{P}) + b_n \sin(\frac{2\pi nt}{P})) * \beta \quad (14)$$

where P is the time series' period. N represents the number of sine and cosine pairs included in the Fourier series, and a_n and b_n are the coefficients of the Fourier coefficients. β is a smoothing prior imposed on the seasonality, where $\beta \sim Normal(0, \sigma^2)$ [32]. If a user selects *Daily* seasonality, $N = 4$. If *Weekly* seasonality is selected, $N = 3$, and $N = 10$ when *Yearly* seasonality is selected [34]. If the user selects *Auto* for seasonality, then $s(t)$ is selected based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) [32]. If *None* is selected, the $s(t)$ term disappears from the model [32].

4.3. Irregular Events Component, $h(t)$

The final component of the Prophet model, $h(t)$, allows the user to consider the effect of major holidays in the model fitting and forecasting process. Specifically, users can specify dates to be treated as "holidays," where the effect of each selected date is independent [32]. Therefore, the irregular events component is given by [32]:

$$h(t) = [\mathbf{1}(t \in D_1), \dots, \mathbf{1}(t \in D_i)]\kappa \quad (15)$$

where D_i is the past and future dates for a given holiday, i , and $\mathbf{1}$ is an indicator representing if time t falls during holiday i [32]. Finally, κ corresponds to the change in the forecast, where $\kappa \sim Normal(0, v^2)$ [32].

4.4. Software Specifications

We employ the *prophet()* function from the "prophet" package for model fitting [33]. As discussed above, users can select either a *linear* or *flat* growth trend assumption as part of the model-fitting process.

Additionally, users have multiple seasonality assumption options with the default set to *Auto* [33].

Finally, suppose some holidays should be considered as part of the model fitting and forecasting process.

In that case, users can select multiple holidays (i.e., dates) via the calendar in the sidebar panel. However, the dashboard defaults to considering no holidays or special dates. We utilize the *predict()* function from the "stats" package to obtain model forecasts and fitted values [22].

5. Performance Metrics

Users can evaluate both the model fit and forecast performance using mean squared error (MSE), mean absolute error (MAE), weighted interval scores (WIS), coverage of the prediction interval (PI coverage), weighted interval scores (WIS), Winkler Scores, and Skill Scores. A more detailed description of the performance metrics can be found in [12, 35], and Winkler and Skill Scores are discussed in further detail within the main manuscript. We also provide the corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) to evaluate the model fit of the ARIMA, GLM, and GAM models, as well as the results of the Ljung-Box test for the ARIMA model. Additional details regarding the Ljung-Box test can be found in [13].

5.1. Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

MAE and MSE assess deviations in the mean model fit from the original time series data [36]. Specifically, MAE is given by [36]:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{h=1}^N |\hat{y}_t - y_t|, \quad (16)$$

and MSE by [36]:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{h=1}^N (\hat{y}_t - y_t)^2. \quad (17)$$

In both equations, y_t is the original data of the process of interest at time point t , and \hat{y}_t is the model fit or forecasted value at time t . N represents the total length of time under evaluation (i.e., calibration or forecast period).

5.2. PI Coverage (PI coverage) and Weighted Interval Scores (WIS)

The dashboard provides PI coverage and WIS as measures of model fit and forecast uncertainty. PI coverage represents the proportion of observed data within the PI selected by the user. The WIS, described in [35], provides quantiles of the predictive forecast distribution by combining a set of interval scores (IS) from probabilistic forecasts [37]. Only a central $(1 - \alpha) * 100\%$ PI is needed to calculate an IS [37] as indicated below:

$$IS_{\alpha}(F, y) = (u - l) + \frac{2}{\alpha} * (l - y) * \mathbf{1}(y < l) + \frac{2}{\alpha} * (y - u) * \mathbf{1}(y > u). \quad (18)$$

$\mathbf{1}$ is an indicator function, where $\mathbf{1}(y < l) = 1$ if $y < l$ and 0 otherwise. The $\frac{\alpha}{2}$ and $1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}$ quantiles of the forecast F are represented by l and u . The IS consists of three distinct quantities [37]:

1. The sharpness of F , given by the width $u - l$ of the central $(1 - \alpha) \times 100\%$ PI.
2. A penalty term $\frac{2}{\alpha} * (l - y) * \mathbf{1}(y < l)$ for the observations that fall below the lower end point l of the $(1 - \alpha) \times 100\%$ PI. This penalty term is directly proportional to the distance between y and the lower end l of the PI. The strength of the penalty depends on the level.
3. An analogous penalty term $\frac{2}{\alpha} * (y - u) * \mathbf{1}(y > u)$ for the observations falling above the upper limit u of the PI.

As indicated in the “Quantile Forecast” box on the *Forecasting* page, the dashboard provides multiple central PIs at different levels $(1 - \alpha_1) < (1 - \alpha_2) < \dots < (1 - \alpha_k)$. Additionally, the central prediction interval at level $1 - \alpha_0 \rightarrow 0$ is provided in the first column of the box (m). From this, the WIS is calculated by [35, 38, 39]:

$$WIS_{\alpha_0:K}(F, y) = \frac{1}{K + \frac{1}{2}} * (w_0 * |y - m| + \sum_{k=1}^K w_k * IS_{\alpha_k}(F, y)) \quad (19)$$

where, $w_k = \frac{\alpha_k}{2}$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ and $w_0 = \frac{1}{2}$.

5.3. Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)

The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) is frequently used to select, evaluate, and compare model fits [40, 41]. It is as follows [41]:

$$AIC = -2LL + (2k) \quad (20)$$

where LL is the log-likelihood, k represents the number of parameters included in the model and the calibration period length is given by n . The AIC for the model fit is directly available as part of the *auto.arima()* function [14]. However, for the GLM and GAM models, the AIC must be manually calculated using (20). The dashboard obtains the log-likelihood directly from the GLM and GAM fits, utilizing the *logLik()* function [42]. The AIC only applies to frequent methods, so the dashboard will not supply the value for the Prophet model, a Bayesian framework.

5.4. Corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc)

The bias-corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc) is a variation of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) that adjusts for small sample sizes [41]. It is as follows:

$$AICc = -2LL + (2k) + \frac{2*k*(k+1)}{n-k-1} \quad (21)$$

where LL is the log-likelihood, k represents the number of parameters included in the model, and the calibration period length is given by n . The AICc for the model fit is directly available as part of the *auto.arima()* function [14]. However, for the GLM and GAM models, the AICc must be manually calculated using (21). The dashboard obtains the log-likelihood directly from the GLM and GAM fits, utilizing the *logLik()* function [42]. The AICc only applies to frequent methods, so the dashboard will not supply the value for the Prophet model, a Bayesian framework.

5.5. Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC)

The Bayesian information criterion (BIC), also known as Schwarz's Bayesian criterion (SBC), is frequently applied in the model selection process [43]. As with the AIC, the BIC is available for any model where the log-likelihood can be calculated [43]. It is given by the following [41]:

$$BIC = -2LL + k * \log(n) \tag{22}$$

where LL is the log-likelihood, k represents the number of parameters included in the model and the calibration period length is given by n . The BIC for the model fit is directly available as part of the *auto.arima()* function [14]. However, for the GLM and GAM models, the BIC must be manually calculated using (22). The dashboard obtains the log-likelihood directly from the GLM and GAM fits, utilizing the *logLik()* function [42]. The BIC only applies to frequent methods, so the dashboard will not supply the value for the Prophet model, a Bayesian framework.

References

1. Furtado P. Epidemiology SIR with regression, arima, and Prophet in forecasting COVID-19. *Engineering Proceedings*. 2021;5(1):52. doi: 10.3390/engproc2021005052.
2. Benvenuto D, Giovanetti M, Vassallo L, Angeletti S, Ciccozzi M. Application of the ARIMA model on the COVID-2019 epidemic dataset. *Data Brief*. 2020;29:105340. doi:10.1016/j.dib.2020.105340.
3. Abolmaali S, Shirzaei S. A comparative study of SIR Model, Linear Regression, Logistic Function and ARIMA Model for forecasting COVID-19 cases. *AIMS Public Health*. 2021;8(4):598-613. doi:10.3934/publichealth.2021048.
4. Sah S, Surendiran B, Dhanalakshmi R, Mohanty SN, Alenezi F, Polat K. Forecasting COVID-19 pandemic using Prophet, ARIMA, and hybrid stacked LSTM-GRU models in India. *Comput Math Methods Med*. 2022;2022:1556025. doi:10.1155/2022/1556025.
5. Alghamdi T, Elgazzar K, Bayoumi M, Sharaf T, Shah S. Forecasting traffic congestion using ARIMA modeling. In: *2019 15th international wireless communications & mobile computing conference (IWCMC)*. IEEE. 2019;1227-1232. doi: 10.1109/IWCMC.2019.8766698.
6. Ariyo AA, Adewumi AO, Ayo CK. Stock price prediction using the ARIMA model. In: *2014 UKSim-AMSS 16th International Conference on Computer Modelling and Simulation*. IEEE. 2014; 106-112. doi: 10.1109/UKSim.2014.67.
7. Tektaş M. Weather forecasting using ANFIS and ARIMA models. *Environ Res Eng Manag*. 2010;51(1):5-10.

8. Yenidoğan I, Çayır A, Kozan O, Dağ T, Arslan Ç. Bitcoin forecasting using ARIMA and PROPHET. In: *2018 3rd international conference on computer science and engineering (UBMK)*. IEEE. 2018; 621-624. doi: 10.1109/UBMK.2018.8566476.
9. Samal KKR, Babu KS, Das SK, Acharaya A. Time series based air pollution forecasting using SARIMA and prophet model. In: *Proceedings of the 2019 International Conference on Information Technology and Computer Communications*. 2019; 80-85. doi: 10.1145/3355402.3355417.
10. Bleichrodt A, Dahal S, Maloney K, Casanova L, Luo R, Chowell G. Real-time forecasting the trajectory of monkeypox outbreaks at the national and global levels, July–October 2022. *BMC Med*. 2023;21(1):19. doi: 10.1186/s12916-022-02725-2.
11. Chowell G, Dahal S, Tariq A, Roosa K, Hyman JM, Luo R. An ensemble n-sub-epidemic modeling framework for short-term forecasting epidemic trajectories: Application to the COVID-19 pandemic in the USA. *PLoS Comput Biol*. 2022;18(10):e1010602. doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010602.
12. Bleichrodt A, Luo R, Kirpich A, Chowell G. Evaluating the forecasting performance of ensemble sub-epidemic frameworks and other time series models for the 2022–2023 mpox epidemic. *R Soc Open Sci*. 2024;11(7):240248. doi:10.1098/rsos.240248.
13. Hyndman RJ, Athanasopoulos G. *Forecasting: principles and practice*. Melbourne, Australia: OTexts; 2021. <https://otexts.com/fpp3/>.
14. Hyndman R. auto.arima: Fit best ARIMA model to univariate time series (version 8.23.0). *Rdocumentation*. <https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/forecast/versions/8.23.0/topics/auto.arima>. Published June 19, 2024. Accessed December 30, 2024.

15. Hyndman R. forecast (version 8.23.0). *RDocumentation*.
<https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/forecast/versions/8.23.0>. Published June 19, 2024.
Accessed December 30, 2024.
16. Agresti A. *Introduction to Categorical Data Analysis*. 2nd ed. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. ;
2007.
17. Roback P, Legler J. *Beyond multiple linear regression: applied generalized linear models
and multilevel models in R*. Chapman and Hall/CRC; 2021.
18. Kida Y. Generalized linear models: Introduction to advanced statistical modeling. *Towards
Data Science*. <https://towardsdatascience.com/generalized-linear-models-9cbf848bb8ab>.
Published September 23, 2019. Accessed December 30, 2024.
19. Venables WN, Ripley BD. *Modern Applied Statistics with S*. 4 ed. Statistics and Computing.
New York, New York: Springer; 2002.
20. R-core. glm: Fitting Generalized Linear Models (version 3.6.2). *RDocumentation*.
<https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/stats/versions/3.6.2/topics/glm>. Accessed
December 30, 2024.
21. Ripley B. glm.nb: Fit a Negative Binomial Generalized Linear Model (version 7.3-60.0.1).
RDocumentation. [https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/MASS/versions/7.3-
60.0.1/topics/glm.nb](https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/MASS/versions/7.3-60.0.1/topics/glm.nb). Published January 13, 2024. Accessed December 30, 2024.
22. R-core. predict: Model Predictions (version 3.6.2). *RDocumentation*.
<https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/stats/versions/3.6.2/topics/predict>. Accessed
December 30, 2024.

23. Shafi A. What are Generalised Additive Models? *Towards Data Science*.
<https://towardsdatascience.com/generalised-additive-models-6dfbedf1350a>. Published May 18, 2021. Accessed December 30, 2024.
24. Wood SN. *Generalized Additive Models: An Introduction with R, Second Edition*. CRC Press; 2017:496.
25. Wood S. gam: Generalized additive models with integrated smoothness estimation (version 1.9-1). *RDocumentation*. <https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/mgcv/versions/1.9-1/topics/gam>. Published December 20, 2023. Accessed December 30, 2024.
26. Smooth terms in GAM. *RDocumentation*. <https://stat.ethz.ch/R-manual/R-devel/library/mgcv/html/smooth.terms.html>. Accessed December 30, 2024.
27. Xie C, Wen H, Yang W, et al. Trend analysis and forecast of daily reported incidence of hand, foot and mouth disease in Hubei, China by Prophet model. *Sci Rep*. 2021;11(1):1445. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-81100-2.
28. Navratil M, Kolkova A. Decomposition and forecasting time series in the business economy using prophet forecasting model. *Cent Eur Bus Rev*. 2019;8(4):26. doi: [10.18267/j.cebr.221](https://doi.org/10.18267/j.cebr.221).
29. Jha BK, Pande S. Time series forecasting model for supermarket sales using FB-prophet. In: *2021 5th International Conference on Computing Methodologies and Communication (ICCMC)*. IEEE. 2021; 547-554. doi: 10.1109/ICCMC51019.2021.9418033.
30. Kirpich A, Shishkin A, Weppelmann TA, Tchernov AP, Skums P, Gankin Y. Excess mortality in Belarus during the COVID-19 pandemic as the case study of a country with limited non-pharmaceutical interventions and limited reporting. *Sci Rep*. 2022;12(1):5475. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-09345-z.

31. Shishkin A, Lhewa P, Yang C, et al. Excess mortality in Ukraine during the course of COVID-19 pandemic in 2020–2021. *Sci Rep.* 2023;13(1):6917. doi:10.1038/s41598-023-33113-2.
32. Taylor SJ, Letham B. Forecasting at scale. *Am Stat.* 2018;72(1):37-45. doi:10.1080/00031305.2017.1380080.
33. Taylor S. prophet: Prophet forecaster (version 1.0). *RDocumentation.* <https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/prophet/versions/1.0/topics/prophet>. Published March 30, 2021. Accessed December 30, 2024.
34. Rafferty G. *Forecasting Time Series Data with Facebook Prophet: Build, improve, and optimize time series forecasting models using the advanced forecasting tool.* Packt Publishing Ltd; 2021.
35. Chowell G, Dahal S, Bleichrodt A, Tariq A, Hyman JM, Luo R. SubEpiPredict: A tutorial-based primer and toolbox for fitting and forecasting growth trajectories using the ensemble n -sub-epidemic modeling framework. *Infect Dis Model.* 2024; 9(2):411-436. doi:10.1016/j.idm.2024.02.001.
36. Kuhn M, Johnson K. *Applied predictive modeling.* Nol 26. New York, New York: Springer; 2013.
37. Gneiting T, Raftery AE. Strictly Proper Scoring Rules, Prediction, and Estimation. *J Am Stat Assoc.* 2007/3/1 2007;102(477):359-378. doi:10.1198/016214506000001437
38. Bracher J, Ray EL, Gneiting T, Reich NG. Evaluating epidemic forecasts in an interval format. *PLoS Comput Biol.* 2022 Oct 5;18(10):e1010592. doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010592]. *PLoS Comput Biol.* 2021;17(2):e1008618. Published 2021 Feb 12. doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008618.

39. Cramer EY, Ray EL, Lopez VK, et al. Evaluation of individual and ensemble probabilistic forecasts of COVID-19 mortality in the United States. [published correction appears in Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A. 2023 Apr 11;120(15):e2304076120. doi:10.1073/pnas.2304076120]. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2022;119(15):e2113561119. doi:10.1073/pnas.2113561119.
40. Akaike H. Information theory and an extension of the maximum likelihood principle. *Selected papers of hirotugu akaike*. Springer; 1998:199-213.
41. Spiess A-N, Neumeyer N. An evaluation of R² as an inadequate measure for nonlinear models in pharmacological and biochemical research: a Monte Carlo approach. *BMC Pharmacol*. 2010;10:1-11. doi:10.1186/1471-2210-10-6.
42. R-Core. *logLik: Extract Log-Likelihood* (version 3.6.2). *RDocumentation*. <https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/stats/versions/3.6.2/topics/logLik>. Accessed December 30, 2024.
43. Doug. *BIC: Bayesian Information Criterion* (version 0.999375-37). *RDocumentation*. <https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/lme4/versions/0.999375-37/topics/BIC>. Published November 10, 2010. Accessed December 30, 2024.